

doi:10.5281/zenodo.18208922

Parent-Teacher Control Mechanisms and Teenage Substance Abuse in Nkpolu Community Secondary School, Rivers State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the influence of parent-teacher control mechanisms on teenage substance abuse at Nkpolu Community Secondary School in Rivers State, Nigeria. Against the backdrop of rising adolescent drug use in Nigeria's urban and peri-urban communities, the research investigates how family and school environments shape students' exposure to and engagement with substances such as tobacco, alcohol, and inhalants. Guided by Social Control and Social Learning theories, the study employs a qualitative methodology, conducting 37 in-depth interviews with students, parents, and teachers to capture the lived realities and social dynamics surrounding substance use. The interview data was analyzed using thematic approach and the findings reveal that substance abuse among students is primarily driven by peer influence, accessibility, and the use of inhalants as coping mechanisms for stress. Parental monitoring, characterized by close supervision, emotional engagement, and open communication, emerges as a critical protective factor, while economic pressures and parental absence can undermine this role. Teachers also play a significant part in prevention, providing moral guidance and active supervision, though their impact is often limited by resource constraints and inconsistent engagement. The study further highlights the importance of collaboration between parents and teachers; where such partnerships exist, they reinforce positive behaviors and strengthen prevention efforts. The research concludes that effective prevention of teenage substance abuse in Nkpolu requires integrated, community-based strategies that strengthen both family and school social controls. Recommendations include enhanced parent-teacher engagement, improved school-based psychosocial support, and context-specific interventions tailored to the socio-economic realities of the community. This study contributes localized insights to the broader discourse on adolescent substance abuse prevention in Nigeria and similar settings.

Keywords: substance abuse, control mechanisms, parents, teachers

INTRODUCTION

Substance abuse among teenagers has become a critical global public health concern with severe implications for individual development, educational attainment, public safety, and national productivity. Across various countries, adolescents are increasingly engaging in the use of psychoactive substances—ranging from alcohol and cannabis to prescription drugs and synthetic opioids—despite being at a vulnerable stage of physical, psychological, and social development. In Nigeria, this trend has escalated in recent years, drawing the attention of policymakers, educators, parents, and researchers. The 2018 National Survey on Drug Use and Health conducted by the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC) revealed a disturbing pattern: approximately 14.3 million Nigerians aged 15 to 64 had used drugs in the past year, with cannabis being the most frequently abused substance. More significantly, the

report highlighted a rising pattern of drug use among youths aged 15–24 years, signaling a growing epidemic among in-school adolescents and young people (UNODC, 2018). Adolescent substance abuse is particularly pronounced in urban and peri-urban settings like Rivers State, where a confluence of socio-economic challenges, peer influence, poor parenting, and weak institutional oversight converge to increase the vulnerability of young people. According to data from the National Drug Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA), secondary schools in economically disadvantaged and densely populated communities, such as those in Port Harcourt and its environs, are becoming centers for the use and distribution of illicit substances such as cannabis, tramadol, codeine-based cough syrups, and even household items repurposed for recreational highs, like adhesives and aerosol sprays (NDLEA, 2021).

Despite the alarming statistics and the increasing visibility of teenage substance abuse, existing empirical studies in Nigeria have often approached the issue from a generalist or macro-level perspective. While many of these studies highlight key risk factors—such as peer pressure, unemployment, urban poverty, and youth alienation—very few provide an in-depth examination of how parent-teacher control mechanisms specifically influence adolescents' exposure to, and involvement in, substance use. For instance, Obot (2013) acknowledged the role of poor parental monitoring and lack of family cohesion in fostering youth vulnerability to drugs, yet the study stopped short of examining how parent-school collaboration could mitigate such risks. Similarly, Oshodi, Aina, and Onajole (2010), in their study of Lagos-based secondary school students, found that a lack of structured teacher engagement and disciplinary clarity increased the likelihood of students engaging in risky behaviors. However, their research, like many others, treats the role of school-based control mechanisms as peripheral, without exploring how they interact with parental oversight to shape student behavior.

Furthermore, most national studies tend to focus on large metropolitan cities such as Lagos, Abuja, or Kano, often overlooking smaller urban centers or semi-urban communities where the risks of substance abuse may be equally high due to high youth population density, economic hardship, and inadequate supervision. In Rivers State—particularly in under-researched communities like Nkpolu—there is a dearth of empirical data on how community dynamics, parent-child relationships, and teacher-student interactions influence adolescent exposure to drugs. This oversight is problematic because such communities, often characterized by poor infrastructure, limited social amenities, and informal economies, are more likely to experience weak social control mechanisms, making teenagers vulnerable to substance abuse. In addition, most awareness and intervention efforts in Nigeria tend to focus on law enforcement responses, drug testing, and occasional school-based sensitization programs, without addressing the underlying structural issues that impair adult supervision in the home and at school. There remains an insufficient understanding of how parents and teachers can form a cooperative framework to effectively monitor and guide adolescents, particularly within communities where traditional family and school structures are under strain due to modernization, economic displacement, and poor governance.

This study, therefore, addresses a critical gap in both literature and practice by specifically examining the influence of parent-teacher control mechanisms on teenage substance abuse within a local, underexplored community setting. By focusing on Nkpolu Community Secondary School in Rivers State, this research aims to generate localized, evidence-based insights on how the relationships between parents, teachers, and students either act as protective factors or contribute to substance use risks. It contributes uniquely by situating the control functions of both parents and teachers at the center of its analytical framework, thereby providing a nuanced understanding of their roles in addressing the rising tide of adolescent substance abuse. Hence, the study provides answers to four questions:

- i. What is the prevalence and what are the most commonly abused substances among students in Nkpolu Community Secondary School?
- i. In what ways does parental monitoring and control influence the use of substances by teenagers in the study area?
- ii. How do teachers' supervisory roles and moral influence affect teenage substance use in the school?
- iii. How does collaboration between parents and teachers impact efforts to curb substance abuse among students in the community?

Literature Review

Empirical investigations into adolescent substance use and the role of parental and teacher control have illuminated diverse patterns and influential factors across African contexts, particularly Nigeria. For instance, Adelekan (2000) employed a descriptive epidemiological approach to investigate substance use patterns among young people across various African countries. Using comprehensive survey data, the study examined the prevalence of commonly used substances such as alcohol, tobacco, and cannabis among adolescents and young adults. Adelekan's work highlighted alarmingly high rates of substance use, revealing that these behaviors were widespread and often initiated at early ages. The study paid particular attention to the role of the family environment, noting that parental behaviors, supervision levels, and the presence or absence of family support systems significantly influenced youth substance use. Peer influence also emerged as a critical factor, with adolescents who associated with substance-using peers being much more likely to engage in similar behaviors themselves. This epidemiological overview provided a foundational understanding of the contextual factors that drive substance use in African youth populations, stressing the importance of addressing both home and social environments in prevention efforts. Furthermore, Adelekan's findings underscored the necessity of integrated control mechanisms that combine parental oversight with effective involvement from educational institutions. The study argued that efforts to curb substance abuse among youths would be inadequate if they focus solely on either the family or the school environment in isolation. Instead, a coordinated approach was recommended, where parents, teachers, and community stakeholders collaboratively reinforce norms against substance use and provide consistent monitoring and guidance. This conceptual framework anticipates later findings in Nigerian contexts, where the interplay between parental control and teacher authority is seen as vital in managing adolescent behavior. Adelekan's research thus set the stage for more localized studies that explore how these dynamics operate within specific cultural and institutional settings across Africa.

Atwoli and colleagues (2011) carried out a cross-sectional survey targeting college students in Eldoret to assess the prevalence of substance use and identify the factors associated with it. Utilizing structured questionnaires, the study gathered detailed information about students' use of substances such as alcohol, tobacco, and other drugs, as well as their social and familial contexts. The research revealed a considerable level of substance use among college students, with peer pressure emerging as a powerful influence encouraging experimentation and continued use. Additionally, the findings highlighted the critical role of parental supervision, or rather the lack thereof, in increasing vulnerability to substance use. Students reporting minimal parental monitoring were significantly more likely to engage in substance use, suggesting that gaps in parental control could leave adolescents susceptible to negative peer influences. The study's conclusions align closely with observations from similar research conducted in Nigeria, reinforcing the notion that deficits in parental control are a substantial risk factor for youth substance use across different African contexts. Atwoli et al.'s findings also emphasize the complementary role of educational institutions and teachers, who have daily access to students and can provide consistent behavioral oversight and moral guidance. This underscores the importance of a dual approach in intervention strategies—where both home and school environments actively collaborate to regulate adolescent behaviors. By highlighting these dynamics, the study contributes to a broader understanding of how family and institutional controls intersect and the necessity for their integration in effective substance use prevention among young people.

Chukwuemeka and Onyene (2017) conducted an in-depth investigation into the interplay of peer pressure, parental influence, and teacher control on students' tendencies toward drug abuse within the Nigerian context, focusing specifically on secondary school students in Rivers State. Their study employed a mixed-method approach, combining quantitative surveys with qualitative focus group discussions to capture both the prevalence and underlying dynamics of substance use behaviors. The findings demonstrated that effective parental monitoring and teacher-imposed discipline each independently contributed to lowering the likelihood of drug abuse among adolescents. More importantly, the study revealed that when both parents and teachers actively engaged in regulating student behavior, the protective effect against drug abuse was significantly stronger. Nonetheless, the research also identified a critical obstacle: poor communication and limited coordination between home and school environments,

which undermined the overall effectiveness of adolescent behavior control measures. These results closely resonate with those of Okpala and Okoye (2015), who explored parent-teacher collaboration in Enugu State secondary schools through a correlational design. Their research highlighted the importance of consistent messaging and a strong partnership between parents and teachers in improving adolescent behavioral outcomes. Okpala and Okoye's findings emphasize that the alignment of expectations and joint efforts in monitoring adolescents serve as vital mechanisms for behavioral regulation. Together, these studies underscore a key conceptual insight: the synergy between parental and teacher control is essential in combating adolescent drug abuse, and addressing the communication gap between these two spheres remains a pivotal challenge for intervention strategies in Nigerian schools.

Eze (2021) conducted a quantitative survey study in Port Harcourt to examine the impact of drug abuse on students' academic performance. His research revealed a significant negative correlation between substance use and academic achievement, emphasizing that students involved in drug abuse were more likely to experience poor academic outcomes. The study identified parental neglect and teacher leniency as key factors that contributed to substance use, suggesting that when parental control weakens, the role of teachers in enforcing discipline and promoting positive academic behaviors becomes critically important. Eze's findings thus highlight the dual responsibility of family and school environments in shaping adolescents' academic trajectories and mitigating the adverse effects of substance use. Building on the theme of control mechanisms, Nwankwo and Eze (2019) extended the inquiry across multiple Nigerian states using a survey design to explore how family and school environments influence adolescent substance use. Their study uncovered distinct urban-rural differences, noting that urban adolescents had higher exposure to substances, but also generally benefited from more structured and consistent school-based controls. This urban-rural disparity was further elaborated by Nwankwo, Obi, and Nwankwo (2020), who conducted a comparative survey on parental control styles and adolescent risky behaviors. Their findings indicated that authoritative parenting—marked by a balance of warmth and firm control—was particularly effective in rural settings where community cohesion reinforced behavioral norms. Conversely, inconsistent and less structured parental control was more common in urban areas, weakening adolescents' behavioral regulation and increasing vulnerability to substance use. Together, these studies emphasize that both family and school controls are vital, but their effectiveness can vary depending on the socio-environmental context, underscoring the need for context-specific interventions.

Oshodi, Aina, and Onajole (2010) carried out a comprehensive survey among secondary school students in urban Nigeria to determine the prevalence of substance use and identify its key determinants. Their large-scale study revealed that peer influence was a significant factor encouraging initiation into substance use, while parental neglect and insufficient teacher supervision further compounded the risk. The research underscored that adolescents exposed to weak parental monitoring and lax school oversight were more vulnerable to engaging in drug use. These findings point to the complex social dynamics within both the home and educational settings that jointly shape adolescent behaviors, illustrating how gaps in supervision from either sphere can create an environment conducive to risky substance use. The results of Oshodi and colleagues' study align closely with the theoretical framework proposed by DiClemente, Hansen, and Ponton (2013), which emphasizes the interconnected roles of family and school environments in influencing adolescent health risk behaviors. According to this framework, risk trajectories among youth are not shaped by isolated factors but through interactive systems involving parental involvement, peer relationships, and institutional control mechanisms. The Nigerian data thus provides empirical support for this model, highlighting the need for integrated intervention strategies that strengthen both parental engagement and teacher supervision to effectively reduce substance use initiation and its associated harms among adolescents.

Also, the National Drug Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA, 2021) annual report provides a crucial, up-to-date national perspective that corroborates the academic findings on adolescent substance use in Nigeria. The report presents comprehensive surveillance data showing persistently high rates of substance use among youths across various states, highlighting that efforts to curb this trend continue to face significant obstacles. Central among these challenges is the fragmentation of prevention and intervention strategies, particularly the lack of coordinated action between families and schools. This disconnect

undermines the effectiveness of programs designed to educate and support adolescents in resisting drug use. The NDLEA's findings emphasize that without stronger integration of family involvement and school-based initiatives, national efforts to prevent substance abuse among young people remain inadequate. The report calls for enhanced collaboration across multiple sectors, urging stakeholders to develop unified frameworks that bridge the gaps between home, school, and community interventions. By reinforcing communication and partnership between parents, teachers, and enforcement agencies, the NDLEA advocates a more holistic and sustained approach to tackling adolescent substance use in Nigeria.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on Social Control Theory and Social Learning Theory as complementary lenses for explaining adolescent substance use while fully retaining their foundational assumptions and empirical foundations. Social Control Theory, pioneered by Hirschi (1969), explains deviant behaviour through the strength or weakness of individuals' bonds to conventional society, specifically attachment, commitment, involvement, and belief. Strong emotional ties to parents and teachers, investment in conventional goals, participation in socially approved activities, and acceptance of societal norms collectively reduce the likelihood of deviance because individuals have more to lose through social disapproval and sanctions. The theory is particularly relevant to adolescent substance use, as weak parental supervision, limited teacher engagement, and poor family-school communication heighten vulnerability to drug and alcohol use. Hirschi and Gottfredson's (1993) extension of the theory through the concept of self-control further emphasizes early childhood socialization by parents and schools as critical to behavioural regulation. Agnew (1991) integrates social control with strain theory, arguing that weak social bonds intensify strain and frustration, which adolescents may manage through maladaptive coping strategies such as substance use. Empirical support from Wiatrowski, Griswold, and Roberts (1981) demonstrates that strong attachments to parents and teachers significantly reduce delinquency and substance abuse, underscoring social bonds as key protective factors.

Social Learning Theory, advanced by Bandura (1977), complements this perspective by explaining how behaviours are actively learned through social interaction, observation, and imitation. The theory identifies attention, retention, reproduction, and motivation as the core mechanisms through which individuals adopt behaviours modeled by peers, family members, or teachers. Bandura emphasizes that behaviour is socially acquired rather than innate, making the social environment central to understanding substance use. Akers' (1998) differential reinforcement theory extends this framework by showing that behaviours persist or decline depending on social rewards or punishments such as peer approval or sanctions. Empirical applications by Sussman, Dent, and Stacy (2002) reveal that positive parental and teacher modeling, consistent monitoring, and supportive relationships significantly reduce adolescent drug use, while Catalano et al. (1996) demonstrate that exposure to pro-social role models and consistent disciplinary practices in family and school settings lowers the likelihood of substance use. When integrated, Social Control Theory explains why strong bonds restrain deviance, while Social Learning Theory explains how behaviours are acquired within social contexts. As Hirschi (1969), Bandura (1977), Akers (1998), and Catalano et al. (1996) collectively suggest, strong family and school bonds both limit exposure to negative models and reinforce positive ones. This combined framework is particularly suited to the Nigerian context, where family structures and school discipline remain central to youth socialization, allowing the study to capture the dynamic interaction between social regulation and learned behaviour in shaping adolescent substance use.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a mixed-methods approach to investigate adolescent substance use within the Nigerian context, with specific attention to parental supervision and teacher discipline as key social influences. Quantitatively, a descriptive survey design was used to capture prevailing patterns and perceptions of substance use and social control, while qualitatively, a participatory research orientation guided the in-depth exploration of lived experiences, meanings, and contextual dynamics surrounding adolescent behavior. The study was conducted at Community Secondary School Nkpolu-Oroworukwo in Rivers State, a setting considered suitable due to its social composition and relevance to the research

problem. The target population comprised students, parents, and teachers associated with the school; although official enrollment figures were not provided by school authorities, an unverified estimate placed the combined population at about 380. Guided by the principle of data saturation rather than statistical representativeness, approximately 55 participants were involved, including about 30 students, 15 parents, and 10 teachers, allowing for depth, diversity of perspectives, and triangulation across groups. Participants were selected using purposive sampling to ensure inclusion of individuals with direct experience and relevant knowledge of adolescent substance use and control mechanisms, such as students within the adolescent age range, actively involved parents, and teachers responsible for discipline and student welfare. Data were collected primarily through in-depth interviews and participant observation, enabling the researcher to elicit detailed narratives, observe school and interpersonal dynamics, and capture contextual factors influencing behavior. Interviews provided a confidential space for discussing sensitive issues, while observations during school activities offered firsthand insight into teacher–student interactions, peer relations, and supervisory practices. Qualitative data were transcribed verbatim and analyzed using thematic analysis, involving systematic coding and identification of recurring patterns and themes aligned with the study objectives, with NVivo software employed to facilitate data organization, coding, and retrieval for rigorous and transparent analysis.

Data Analysis

This section analyzes the qualitative data collected and the analysis focuses on exploring the dynamics of parental supervision, teacher discipline, and their combined influence on adolescent substance use behaviors. Through thematic presentation, it highlights key patterns and insights that emerged from participants' narratives, providing a rich understanding of the social and environmental factors shaping youths' experiences.

Theme 1: Prevalence and Commonly Abused Substances Among Students

The findings from the interviews reveal that substance use among students at Nkpolu Community Secondary School is a notable concern, with varying degrees of prevalence reported by different respondents. Most participants acknowledged that substance use exists among students, although the extent differs according to individual perceptions and experiences within the school environment. Many students admitted to knowing peers who engage in substance use, with common substances including cigarettes, alcohol, and locally available inhalants such as “solution” (a type of glue or chemical solvent). Tobacco use was reported as the most prevalent, often initiated during social interactions or under peer influence. A male student aged 15 shared:

"Many of my friends smoke cigarettes after school hours, especially during breaks. Some even drink alcohol at parties during weekends. It is common, but not everyone uses these substances." (IDI Participant/Male Student/Aged 15 years)

Alcohol consumption was also frequently mentioned, particularly during social gatherings or family ceremonies. Some students revealed that alcohol is sometimes accessed with ease in the community, despite age restrictions. A female student expressed concern:

"I have seen students come to school smelling of alcohol. Some say they drink to feel relaxed or to forget their problems at home." (IDI Participant/Female Student/Aged 16 years)

Teachers confirmed these observations and added that cigarette smoking and alcohol use are the substances most often encountered during school monitoring activities. A female teacher noted:

"Cigarettes and alcohol are definitely the most common substances abused by our students. We occasionally find some smoking hidden in corners or during breaks, and sometimes the smell of alcohol on their breath is evident." (IDI Participant/Female Teacher/Aged 42 years)

Interestingly, inhalant abuse, particularly glue sniffing, was mentioned by both students and parents as a rising concern. This practice is often linked to the students' attempt to cope with stress or escape from difficult home environments. One parent described:

"I heard from other parents that some children are sniffing glue or similar chemicals because they are facing challenges at home and school. It's dangerous and hard to control." (IDI Participant/Male Parent/Aged 44 years)

While some respondents believed that substance use is limited to a minority of students, others highlighted that underreporting might mask the true extent due to fear of punishment or stigma. A male student captured this sentiment:

"Many students hide their use from teachers and parents because they don't want to get into trouble. So, it's hard to say exactly how many are involved." (IDI Participant/Male Student/Aged 17 years)

Theme 2: Influence of Parental Monitoring and Control on Teen Substance Use

Parental monitoring emerged as a key factor influencing adolescent substance use within the Nkpolu Community Secondary School environment. Respondents consistently emphasized that the degree of parental supervision and involvement in their children's lives significantly shaped students' decisions regarding substance use. Where parents maintained close supervision, adolescents reported lower instances of substance engagement, suggesting that attentive parenting serves as a protective barrier against risky behaviors. Several students attributed their avoidance of substance use to the strict oversight exercised by their parents. One female student remarked:

"My parents always check where I am going and who I am with. Because of that, I don't hang out with friends who use drugs or alcohol." (IDI Participant/Female Student/Aged 16 years)

This sentiment was echoed by teachers, who observed that students from homes with consistent parental control showed better behavioral regulation and fewer incidences of substance use. A male teacher explained:

"Students whose parents are involved in their academic and social life tend to stay away from drugs and alcohol. These parents communicate rules clearly and follow up on their children's activities." (IDI Participant/Male Teacher/Aged 38 years)

Conversely, a lack of parental supervision was frequently linked to increased vulnerability to substance use. Many students acknowledged that insufficient parental control often resulted in greater freedom to experiment with substances. A male student disclosed:

"Some of my friends use drugs because their parents are never around to supervise them. They do whatever they want without anyone stopping them." (IDI Participant/Male Student/Aged 15 years)

Parents themselves recognized the importance of monitoring but also admitted that various socio-economic pressures sometimes limited their ability to provide adequate supervision. One mother explained:

"We want to watch our children closely, but with work and other responsibilities, it's hard to always be around. Sometimes they are left alone, and that's when they get involved in bad habits." (IDI Participant/Female Parent/Aged 40 years)

The data also highlighted that the quality of parental monitoring—beyond mere physical presence—matters significantly. Emotional connection, open communication, and clear expectations were cited as essential components of effective parental control. A father noted:

"I always talk to my children about the dangers of drugs and alcohol. It's not just about telling them what not to do but explaining why they should avoid these things." (IDI Participant/Male Parent/Aged 47 years)

The influence of parental monitoring on adolescent substance use in Nkpolu Community Secondary School is complex. Where monitoring is consistent and coupled with meaningful communication, students are less likely to engage in substance use. However, gaps in supervision—often linked to economic and social challenges—create vulnerabilities that increase the likelihood of substance experimentation and abuse. This theme underscores the critical role parents play not only as supervisors but also as educators and role models in shaping their children's behavior.

Theme 3: Teachers' Supervisory Roles and Moral Influence on Teenage Substance Use

The role of teachers in supervising students and serving as moral exemplars emerged as a significant theme influencing substance use behaviors among adolescents at Nkpolu Community Secondary School. Participants described teachers as both authority figures and key influencers who help shape students' attitudes and choices concerning substance use. Teachers' supervision was perceived as a crucial deterrent to drug and alcohol use. Many students reported that regular monitoring by teachers during school hours limited opportunities for substance abuse. A male student shared his experience:

"Teachers always watch us closely during breaks and after school. If they notice anything suspicious, they quickly step in. This makes us think twice before doing anything wrong." (IDI Participant/Male Student/Aged 17 years)

This vigilance by teachers was complemented by their disciplinary actions, which students recognized as a form of moral guidance. A female teacher expressed her commitment to guiding students beyond academics:

"We don't just teach subjects; we try to teach values too. When students see that we care about their behavior, not just their grades, they tend to avoid harmful activities like drugs." (IDI Participant/Female Teacher/Aged 42 years)

However, the impact of teachers' supervisory roles was not solely based on formal discipline. The moral influence teachers exerted through their personal conduct and relationships with students was frequently highlighted. A student remarked:

"Some teachers are like role models; they inspire us to be better. When they talk about staying away from drugs, it feels real because they live what they preach." (IDI Participant/Female Student/Aged 15 years)

Yet, not all interactions were perceived positively. A few respondents pointed out inconsistencies in teacher supervision and a lack of follow-through in addressing substance use, which sometimes undermined the teachers' influence. One male student noted:

"Sometimes teachers see things but don't do anything. That makes some students think they can get away with using drugs." (IDI Participant/Male Student/Aged 16 years)

Teachers themselves acknowledged challenges such as large class sizes and limited resources that hindered their ability to monitor every student closely. A senior teacher remarked: "We want to supervise better, but with many students and few staff, it's hard to catch every problem early. We rely a lot on discipline and moral talks to guide them." (IDI Participant/Male Teacher/Aged 45 years)

Despite these challenges, the consensus was that teachers play a vital role in shaping the school environment and influencing student behavior. Their supervisory presence, combined with efforts to instill moral values, contributes significantly to reducing substance use among adolescents. This theme illustrates how the school's institutional framework, embodied by its teachers, acts as a critical social control mechanism in mitigating risky behaviors.

Theme 4: Collaboration Between Parents and Teachers and Its Impact on Substance Abuse Prevention

The dynamic interplay between parents and teachers emerged as a pivotal factor influencing the effectiveness of efforts to curb substance abuse among students at Nkpolu Community Secondary School. Respondents underscored that joint action and communication between these two key stakeholders create a stronger support network for adolescents, fostering an environment less conducive to substance use. Several parents and teachers emphasized that when collaboration is consistent and transparent, it enhances monitoring and reinforces behavioral expectations both at home and in school. One parent remarked:

"When the teachers call me to discuss my child's behavior, it helps me know what is happening in school. Then I can talk to my child at home and guide him properly." (IDI Participant/Female Parent/Aged 40 years)

Similarly, teachers noted that parental involvement through regular feedback sessions and meetings boosts their capacity to identify students at risk. A female teacher explained: "We cannot do it alone. When parents are involved and willing to cooperate, it becomes easier to track students who might be struggling with peer pressure or substance use." (IDI Participant/Female Teacher/Aged 38 years)

The synergy between parents and teachers was also described as instrumental in creating a consistent message about the dangers of drugs and the importance of discipline. A male parent observed:

"If both the school and the home tell the child the same thing about drugs, the child listens better. Mixed messages confuse them." (IDI Participant/Male Parent/Aged 45 years)

However, some participants pointed out challenges in maintaining this collaboration, citing issues like poor communication channels and occasional lack of parental responsiveness. A male teacher noted: "Sometimes we try to reach out to parents, but some don't respond or come late to meetings. That weakens our efforts because the student sees no united front." (IDI Participant/Male Teacher/Aged 44 years). Despite these setbacks, the majority agreed that fostering strong partnerships between parents and teachers is essential. This collaboration not only increases surveillance and accountability but also provides emotional and moral support to students. As one female student put it:

"When my parents and teachers talk and work together, I feel like I have people watching out for me everywhere. It makes me think twice about getting involved in drugs." (IDI Participant/Female Student/Aged 16 years)

FINDINGS

The interviews at Nkpolu Community Secondary School revealed that tobacco (cigarettes), alcohol, and inhalants such as glue are the most commonly abused substances among students. This aligns with findings by Oshodi, Aina, and Onajole (2010), who identified tobacco and alcohol as prevalent among Nigerian secondary school students, with glue sniffing often used as a coping mechanism in stressful home environments. Similarly, the UNODC (2018, 2023) reports highlight widespread tobacco and alcohol use among youth in Nigeria, attributing rising inhalant use to accessibility and low cost. From a theoretical standpoint, Social Learning Theory (Bandura, 1977) explains these behaviors. Students learn substance use through observation and imitation of peers within their social groups—particularly where smoking and drinking are normalized. The male student's statement about peer use exemplifies modeling behavior and reinforcement processes within peer networks. Additionally, the use of inhalants as a form of stress relief reflects psychological coping mechanisms consistent with self-medication hypotheses. The underreporting of substance use due to stigma or fear of punishment also reflects dynamics described by Social Control Theory (Hirschi, 1969), where deviant behaviors are concealed to avoid sanctions. This suggests the presence of informal social controls but also indicates gaps in open communication about substance use risks, potentially masking the full extent of the problem.

Furthermore, the second finding shows that parental monitoring is a critical protective factor against adolescent substance use. Students with parents who provide close supervision, emotional engagement, and clear communication are less likely to engage in substance abuse. This finding supports Akperi & Raimi (2016) and Adedwale and Aderibigbe's (2017) study in Lagos State, which demonstrated that parental involvement and supervision significantly reduce adolescent risky behaviors. Parental monitoring fits within the Social Control Theory framework, which posits that strong family bonds—characterized by attachment, involvement, and supervision—reduce deviant behavior (Hirschi, 1969). When parents consistently oversee their children and engage in open dialogue about the dangers of substance use, adolescents internalize these norms and avoid such behaviors. The challenges parents face, such as economic pressures limiting supervision time, further underscore the importance of quality parental involvement. The father's comment on emotional communication aligns with Barber's (1996) concept of psychological control, where supportive communication fosters healthier behavioral outcomes.

Thirdly, the study found that teachers' roles extend beyond academics to include moral guidance and supervision, which significantly influence student substance use. Respondents identified teachers as key social control agents who reduce opportunities for substance use through active monitoring and positive role modeling. This aligns with Akinbode's (2014) findings on the importance of teacher-student relationships in regulating student behavior in Nigerian secondary schools. Social Control Theory again offers insight, viewing teachers as institutional enforcers of social norms who help deter deviant behaviors through discipline and role modeling (Hirschi, 1969). Their moral influence helps students internalize expectations related to avoiding drug use. However, inconsistencies in supervision and resource constraints weaken this influence, highlighting structural challenges within schools. This calls

for institutional support to empower teachers, consistent with WHO (2021) recommendations for comprehensive school-based interventions to reduce adolescent substance use.

Finally, the findings in this study notes that the collaboration between parents and teachers is a vital factor in preventing adolescent substance use. When these groups work together, they provide consistent messaging and a united front that reinforces positive behaviors. This finding reflects Obot's (2013) emphasis on community involvement in drug prevention and the NDLEA's (2021) advocacy for integrated family-school approaches. Challenges such as poor communication or parental disengagement weaken prevention efforts and create mixed messages for students. This underscores the need for structured programs to foster consistent parent-teacher engagement, ensuring effective monitoring and support.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, it is safe to conclude that substance abuse among students is influenced by multiple social factors, with tobacco, alcohol, and inhalants are the most commonly used substances. Peer influence is a powerful driver, as students tend to imitate behaviors normalized within their social circles. The use of inhalants as a coping strategy highlights the emotional challenges faced by some students. Despite this, stigma and fear of repercussions contribute to underreporting, which masks the true extent of the issue. Parental involvement emerged as a crucial protective factor, where close supervision, emotional support, and open communication significantly reduce the likelihood of substance use. However, economic and other pressures can restrict the capacity for parental engagement, emphasizing the need for meaningful quality interactions over mere presence. Teachers also play an essential role beyond academics by providing moral guidance and active supervision that reinforce positive social norms, although their impact can be diminished by resource limitations.

Most importantly, the study emphasized that effective prevention depends on strong collaboration between parents and teachers. Consistent communication and a united approach are key to providing adolescents with clear guidance and support. Without such partnership, prevention efforts risk being undermined by mixed messages and lack of coordination. Therefore, strategies to combat adolescent substance abuse must prioritize enhancing parental and teacher engagement and fostering their collaboration to create a supportive, vigilant environment for students.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Following the findings and conclusion reached in this study, the recommendations below are provided to help address the issue of parent-teacher control and substance abuse among teenagers.

- Schools should implement peer-led awareness campaigns and support groups to address the influence of peer pressure in substance use. Empowering positive peer role models can help change norms around tobacco, alcohol, and inhalant use.
- Initiatives to educate parents on effective supervision, emotional communication, and the importance of quality engagement should be prioritized. Workshops and support groups can help parents overcome economic and social challenges to better monitor and guide their children.
- Provide teachers with training and resources to improve their capacity for supervision and moral guidance. Schools should establish clear policies and support systems that enable teachers to effectively identify and intervene in substance abuse cases.
- Develop formal platforms and programs that foster regular communication and cooperation between parents and teachers. Such collaboration ensures consistent messaging and unified efforts in preventing adolescent substance abuse within the school community.

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